

Supply-Side Innovations to Increase Equitable Access to Digital Financial Services: Experimental Evidence from Mozambique

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Acknowledgments and Declaration of Interests

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Author Contributions

MK: Data curation; Formal analysis; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing. CB: Data curation; Investigation; Project administration; Writing - review & editing. MH: Conceptualization; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Project administration; Supervision; Writing - review & editing. MM: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Supervision; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing. All authors agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work. All authors had full access to the study data and have accessed and verified the data over the course of the study period.

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Data Availability

De-identified data are available upon reasonable request. A replication dataset and code is available on the Harvard Dataverse at <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/LXRBOU>.

Abstract

Access to digital financial services has expanded in Sub-Saharan Africa, but this expansion may not be distributed equitably. Improved access may require increased engagement with traditionally under-served groups, particularly women. In collaboration with M-Pesa in Mozambique, we worked with Telephonic Sales Representatives (TSRs) to target outreach efforts towards populations that are less likely to utilize mobile money accounts. TSRs were divided into teams by gender and were trained to support clients with opening M-Pesa accounts after clients had purchased a SIM card. We randomized the market that male or female TSR teams were sent to each day. Midway through the intervention, we introduced incentives for enrolling women in rural areas into M-Pesa. We assessed the impact of gendered outreach and incentives on new SIM card registrations and clients enrollment into M-Pesa accounts. Although female TSR teams registered fewer clients to SIM cards relative to male TSR teams, they were more successful at converting clients to M-Pesa, resulting in similar overall M-Pesa enrollments. Introducing incentives to engage with female clients in remote areas also increased overall M-Pesa enrollment rates, particularly among female TSR teams. We find that supply-side innovations can be effective in increasing digital service access and utilization.

Keywords: mobile money; digital financial services; M-Pesa; gender; financial inclusion; Mozambique

JEL Codes: J13, J16, O15, O33, I15, Z13.

1 Introduction

In 2019, the number of mobile money accounts (MMAs) in the world surpassed one billion ([GSM Association, 2019c](#)). Sub-Saharan Africa remains the global epicenter of the use and expansion of mobile money (MM). In 2018, the region was host to almost half (396 million) of all globally registered MMAs and added almost 50 million new MMAs from the previous year alone ([GSM Association, 2017, 2019c](#)). The rapid expansion of MM and digital financial services (DFS) in Sub-Saharan Africa has generated significant benefits for the region, particularly for low-income households without access to formal banking ([Aker et al., 2016](#); [Aker and Mbiti, 2010](#); [Aron, 2018](#); [Jack and Suri, 2011](#); [Mbiti and Weil, 2015](#)). To this end, governments have begun to leverage the spread of digital technologies, from automated wage payments to mobile healthcare (mHealth), to more effectively and transparently deliver services to their constituents. In the same way, the demand for digitizing and streamlining payments has also increased in the private and non-profit sectors, where mobile

telephone networks (MTNs) have been engaged as partners in efforts to improve efficiency and expand access to services ([Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, 2021](#)).

In spite of the progress that has been made over the past two decades, significant gaps in MM access and use persist in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly for women. In low- and middle-income countries, women are 13 percent less likely to own a mobile phone and are 37 percent less likely to have access to mobile internet services, both of which impede women’s access to MM ([GSM Association, 2020](#)). Globally, MMA ownership among women is about 7 percentage points (p.p.) lower than account ownership among men, and these gender gaps in account ownership have persisted over time ([GSM Association, 2020](#)). Analyses of the MM market have identified several key barriers that prevent women from adopting DFS, including: 1) a lack of awareness among women of MM options and the benefits associated with DFS; 2) a lack of access to MM agents who are available and whom women can trust; 3) a lack of confidence among women in their ability to use MM services; and 4) low financial literacy among women ([Penicaud-Scharwatt and Minischetti, 2014](#); [Schaner, 2018](#)).

In this study, we seek to address the limited visibility and representation of women in DFS, along with low levels of MM engagement among women and residents of remote, hard-to-reach areas of Mozambique. We evaluate a suite of supply-side interventions aimed at reducing these barriers and increasing women’s MM uptake. The interventions were designed to expand women’s access to M-Pesa, a leading MM service in Sub-Saharan Africa, by: 1) increasing client awareness and knowledge of M-Pesa at the time of registration; 2) expanding women’s representation in MM by increasing the number of female MM agents, known locally as Telephonic Sales Representatives (TSRs); and 3) offering targeted incentives to encourage TSRs to engage more intensively with female clients, particularly in remote areas.

The interventions were implemented in 10 rural markets in Nampula province. To address the issue of representation, the hiring process for new TSRs was modified to ensure that the same numbers of male and female TSRs would be recruited. TSRs were grouped into teams of three by gender, and on each day, gendered (male only or female only) TSR teams were randomly assigned to visit different markets. All TSRs were trained to encourage and support clients to open an M-Pesa account at the time of purchasing a SIM card. After 12 weeks, all TSR teams were simultaneously introduced to an incentive program to encourage TSRs to engage with and register women and clients in more rural markets to M-Pesa. The incentive introduced TSRs to a raffle lottery with

prizes, where raffle tickets were assigned to TSRs based on the number of new female clients they registered to M-Pesa, and particularly female clients registered from markets that were far away from Nampula’s city center.

We find that overall client recruitment and transaction activity were similar for clients engaged by male and female TSR teams. However, we find important differences in the nature of that engagement: male TSR teams sold more SIM cards overall, but female TSR teams were more effective at converting SIM sales into active M-Pesa accounts, to the extent that there was no significant difference in the overall number of M-Pesa clients registered per market day between female and male TSR teams, nor was there any difference in client use of M-Pesa accounts by TSR gender. These findings suggest that female TSR teams were as successful as male TSR teams in fostering client engagement with M-Pesa. The introduction of the incentive had a strong and positive effect across all teams on client enrollment to both SIM cards and M-Pesa. In particular, female TSR teams became even more successful in converting clients to M-Pesa than male TSR teams following the introduction of the incentive. This effect was strongest for new female clients living in remote markets.

Our study contributes to a limited but growing body of evidence on the impact of interventions that seek to promote financial inclusion through improved access to MM and DFS in resource-poor settings (Jack et al., 2013; Jack and Suri, 2011, 2014; Mbiti and Weil, 2015; Riley, 2018). More recently, randomized controlled trials in Kenya, Malawi, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan have documented a range of effects of MM use on savings behavior and transfers (Aggarwal et al., 2020; Blumenstock et al., 2015; Breza et al., 2020; Jack and Habyarimana, 2018; Suri and Jack, 2016). Our work builds on recent experimental evidence by Batista and Vicente (2021), who found that the introduction of MM services to rural households led to increases in transfers and remittances, reductions in households’ vulnerability to shocks, as well as increased migration out of rural areas and to urban areas (Batista and Vicente, 2021).

A number of studies have documented the potential of DFS to increase remittances as well as individual and household savings (Dupas et al., 2018; Morawczynski, 2009; Morawczynski and Pickens, 2009; Suri and Jack, 2016), while other studies have identified the role of MM as a means to insure against risk and negative shocks (Alinaghi, 2019; Batista and Vicente, 2020b; Jack and Suri, 2011; Riley, 2018; Suri et al., 2012). Studies have also identified the potential of MM to shift

household decision making power to women by allowing women to exercise greater control over household finances and resources (Aker et al., 2016; Gichuki and Mulu-Mutuku, 2018), and recent evidence has shown how MM provides low-income women with the means to improve their financial literacy (Batista and Vicente, 2020b; Tiwari et al., 2019). At the same time, evaluations of MM programs have documented the uneven success of MM and DFS adoption both within and across countries, whereby efforts to introduce services have had limited impact (Adjasi et al., 2023).

Given the importance of MM agents to client recruitment and engagement, the study of agent gender, and agent characteristics more generally, is important to understanding client adoption and use of DFS. Observational studies have examined how the gender and characteristics of agents may impact both agent-level and client-level outcomes (Beck et al., 2013; Cull et al., 2018; Hartarska et al., 2014). Other reports have shown that female agents may improve enrollment and retention of both female and male customers and may offer better service than their male counterparts. These studies have noted the benefits from hiring female MM agents to attract a larger female client base, particularly in contexts where social and cultural norms make it challenging for women to interact with men and where female clients may prefer to interact with female agents (Lindsey and Wilson, 2019; Melnyk et al., 2009; Penicaud-Scharwatt and Minischetti, 2014).¹ On the other hand, recent findings have documented how matching MM agents and clients by gender may create opportunities for vendor misconduct and gender-based discrimination, particularly against female clients who may be less informed about MM and DFS (Annan, 2022). Gender-specific barriers may also make recruiting female agents difficult in contexts where a woman’s decision to enroll as an agent may depend on familial and social approval (GSM Association, 2019a,b).

Our experimental findings highlight the importance of gender in promoting agent-client engagement and add to the literature that investigates the nature of the agent-client relationship in mobile banking (Beck et al., 2013; Chamboko et al., 2021; Cull et al., 2018; Rusu and Harten, 2015; Suri and Jack, 2016). More broadly, our findings relate to a larger evidence base on interventions aimed at narrowing gender gaps in the private sector, particularly in contexts where incentives to adopt inclusive policies remain limited (Chatterji et al., 2011; Rindfleish, 2002; Tansel, 2005). As governments increase their reliance on MM to improve the operation of basic goods and services, such as health and social protection (World Bank, 2022), they may be in a position to demand the private sector to take additional steps to improve equity in access to MM tools.

Our findings reinforce earlier evidence suggesting that the expansion of access and agent networks, particularly for women and geographically hard-to-reach populations who likely face additional barriers to accessing and adopting MM services, may require increased outreach and engagement on the part of mobile network operators and providers to meet latent client demand (Aker et al., 2020). Our study complements recent work by (Batista and Vicente, 2021), which showed that increasing outreach of TSRs to rural areas can substantially increase MM uptake. Proposals for supply-side interventions have noted that MM operators need not design a new service, marketing campaign, or distribution model to attract more female customers; rather, reorienting the marketing and distribution of existing services and altering the incentives of TSRs may be enough to ensure greater uptake of DFS by women as well as by men (Aker and Mbiti, 2010; Suri and Jack, 2016). A core contribution of our study is our ability to leverage rich administrative data to track both the adoption and utilization of mobile money services, capturing not only registrations but also subsequent consumer transaction behavior. To this end, we offer new programmatic insights by considering whether typical sales operations can be made more equitable by changing the processes surrounding hiring, training and incentivizing MM agents.

The rest of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes our study setting. Section 3 presents the TSR recruitment process, the incentive program, randomization of TSR teams to markets, and the empirical analysis. We discuss the main results as well as findings from sub-group analyses in Section 4, and we discuss the implications and conclusions of our study in Section 5.

2 Study Setting

2.1 Nampula, Mozambique

The expansion of MM services in Mozambique, and particularly into more rural and remote areas, has been slow, with pronounced impacts on women’s MM adoption. A first order barrier is the low rates of mobile phone ownership, which is especially problematic in Mozambique. Of seven African countries surveyed in the 2019 GSMA’s Mobile Gender Gap Report, the gender gap between men and women in ownership of a mobile phone was the highest in Mozambique at 24 percent (Association, 2020). A closer examination of this data finds that the rural/urban divide is driving this gap: the gender gap in mobile phone ownership in rural Mozambique is 33 percent, compared to only 8 percent in urban Mozambique. Notably, these gender differences do not reflect lower demand

for MM access.² Evidence from Mozambique suggests that when female heads of household are specifically and systematically targeted, there are no differences in the take-up of MMAs between male and female household members (Batista and Vicente, 2020a).

Our study is situated in Nampula province. With an estimated 5.7 million people, Nampula is the most populous province in Mozambique, and its capital city of Nampula has a metro area population of 877,000 as of 2020 (MacroTrends, 2021). The average monthly household income per capita in the province is 8,031 Mozambican Meticals (125.70 USD) per month, and the province has one of the highest poverty incidences in the country, with over 65 percent of the province living below the global poverty line (Baez et al., 2018; Global Data Lab, 2020; Instituto Nacional de Estatística – Moçambique, 2023). With an M-Pesa penetration rate of 37 percent, MM uptake in urban Nampula is one of the lowest relative to the rest of Mozambique, where most urban areas have penetration rates of over 50 percent. On average, MM users in Nampula province have less than 228 Meticals (4 USD) in their accounts, less than the national average, and findings from a recent evaluation of MM use in Mozambique show a significant gender gap in M-Pesa use in Nampula, with men making up a large majority (almost 70 percent) of users in the province (Financial Sector Deepening Mozambique, 2018). Taken together, the findings suggest that significant barriers to MM adoption and financial inclusion continue to exist for a large proportion of the population, and particularly for poor and rural women (Batista and Vicente, 2021).

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Experimental Design

Figure 1 presents the study design and data collection timeline. In collaboration with Vodafone, we collected client registration and transaction data over a 22-week period, from December 15, 2017 to May 15, 2018. Our field experiment consists of two intervention components, a randomized primary intervention with TSRs that was implemented over a 20-week period, starting in week 2, across 10 markets³, and an incentive program that was introduced to all TSRs in the second half of the intervention period, starting in week 12 (day 83 from the start of data collection). The markets were chosen within Nampula province according to their potential demand for SIM / M-Pesa services and their viability to roll out the intervention.

Figure 1 About Here.

3.1.1 SIM Card and M-Pesa Sales

Mobile sales agents, known as TSRs (Telephonic Sales Representatives), are the primary vendors for SIM cards in Mozambique. TSRs sell Vodafone products (SIM cards and mobile minute “top-ups”) in local marketplaces, usually focusing on more urban or peri-urban markets due to convenience and high client volume, among other reasons. TSRs sell SIM cards for mobile phones, and customers who purchase a SIM card have the option to register for M-Pesa. Under the standard practice, TSRs are neither trained nor required to introduce or register SIM customers to M-Pesa, and they typically do not provide customers with support or instruction in setting up with or using M-Pesa.

3.1.2 TSR Selection and Training

As part of Vodafone’s hiring practice, TSR candidates are usually initially found and screened through a subcontractor. After the screening process, M-Pesa requires that candidates participate in a one-week paid training program, during which time they learn how to sell to and register customers to SIMs. As part of this intervention, TSRs were also trained on registering clients to M-Pesa as well as providing clients with an overview of how to use M-Pesa. After completing the training, candidates are tested on the material covered throughout the week, and the highest scorers are offered a position as a TSR. Lower scorers are offered spots as alternates.

Twelve TSRs were hired to work across 10 markets as part of the study, which was implemented in partnership with the NGO, M4All (M4A), and M-Pesa. While an estimated 90 percent of hired M-Pesa TSRs in Mozambique are male, these interventions hired an even number of male and female TSRs to examine the effects of hiring a higher proportion of female TSRs on sales and M-Pesa use. A total of 20 TSR candidates (10 male candidates and 10 female candidates) passed the screening process and participated in the week-long training. Potential candidates were given an assessment, which included a written test, to assess their capacity to perform their roles as promoters and marketers. The top six scoring male and the top six scoring female TSRs⁴ were subsequently offered positions. TSRs were hired using the standard hiring processes and criteria set by Vodacom and M-Pesa, with a focus on hiring an equal number of male and female TSRs. The 12 hired TSRs were divided into four teams of three members each by gender, resulting in two teams of female only TSRs and two teams of male only TSRs.

All twelve TSRs were trained in the M4A SIM sales and M-Pesa registration protocols, which guides TSRs on the process to guide a client who purchases a new SIM to register for M-Pesa. As part

of the process, clients registering for a SIM card were to be automatically defaulted into the M-Pesa sign up process, which differs from the existing Vodacom practice of M-Pesa in Mozambique. To sign up for M-Pesa, an initial deposit of 20 Meticals was required to register the account. This amount would then be immediately available for the client to use; no other fees were charged to clients to enroll into M-Pesa. For clients who complete the M-Pesa registration process, M4A TSRs were instructed on how to review M-Pesa use with each client, including how to deposit, withdraw, and send funds, and how to find their nearest M-Pesa MM agent. M4A TSRs were also trained to actively offer SIM customers the option to register for M-Pesa and make the process as easy as possible by providing instruction and assistance with setup and usage for customers who were unfamiliar with MM and/or who had trouble navigating the interface. These protocols aimed to promote a more in-depth introduction to and discussion of M-Pesa than the typical Vodacom registration process in Mozambique. Tables in the Supplementary Materials present comparisons of the hiring and sales protocols between the M4A TSR approach and standard Vodacom TSR approach, respectively.

3.1.3 Randomization

Using a Python randomization script, TSR teams were randomly assigned to a different market each day from Mondays to Saturdays to sell new SIM cards and to register SIM customers to M-Pesa. Randomization of market assignments for each day was implemented at the TSR team level. A schedule detailing the random assignment of TSR teams to specific markets on specific days was created in advance for the entire study period, and teams were informed of their assigned, randomly selected markets a week in advance. Each day, TSR teams sold SIM cards and registered customers for M-Pesa in their assigned market. The unit of randomization, and main level of variation, is therefore the market-day. Over the 22-week study period, teams were randomly assigned to the same market on different days and therefore revisited markets multiple times over the study period.

3.1.4 Incentive Program

In week 12 (day 83), all TSRs teams were introduced to an incentive program designed to reward them for registering female clients to both SIM cards and M-Pesa accounts, with higher incentives provided to TSRs for registering women in more rural markets.⁵ Prior to this incentive program, M-Pesa's standard practice was to offer monetary bonuses to TSRs who exceeded SIM registration targets, but these bonuses did not reward TSRs for M-Pesa conversions or for registering harder-to-reach clients. The new incentive program expanded the focus from the extensive margin (SIM sales)

to also include the intensive margin (M-Pesa conversions), particularly targeting remote populations.

The incentive program was planned in advance by Vodafone in coordination with the study team; however, TSR teams were not notified about this program until week 12. While it was not proposed as a direct response to TSR performance or program trends, the introduction of the incentives coincided just as Cyclone Idai struck Nampula province and impacted access to services,⁶ raising important considerations about how external shocks may have influenced both the supply- and demand-side dynamics of the intervention. Indeed, prior evidence suggests that MM use increases in the aftermath of adverse shocks, particularly through remittance activity and emergency transfers, which can drive up demand for M-Pesa accounts (Batista and Vicente, 2021; Dupas et al., 2018; Morawczynski, 2009; Suri and Jack, 2016). As part of our analysis, we examine MM uptake trends after the incentive launch in more remote markets where incentives were highest. However, since the timing of the cyclone coincided with the launch of the incentive, we cannot effectively disentangle the effect of the supply-side intervention from any demand-side changes induced by the cyclone.

As part of the incentive structure, TSRs received one raffle ticket (their name entered once in the raffle prize drawing) for every woman who was registered to M-Pesa and two tickets (their name entered twice) for each woman who was registered in one of the three identified rural, harder-to-reach markets in Nampula province. Winners were drawn every two weeks, and two winners were announced for each lottery draw. Winners won 300 Meticals (\$5.00 USD). Every three weeks, an additional winner was drawn to win a low-end smartphone, valued approximately at \$25.00 USD. This monetary amount was chosen in consultation with M-Pesa to approximate incentives the company could sustain over time.

3.1.5 Data Collection

Assigned market locations, SIM card sales, and M-Pesa registrations for each TSR team were tracked throughout the 22-week data collection period across all 10 markets. For completed transactions and sales, data was collected through the M-Pesa client database for 17 weeks to assess M-Pesa use over time. By matching transaction-level outcomes with data on TSR team outreach by market, we are able to assess the extent to which exposure to female TSR teams impacts SIM and M-Pesa registration and use over time, particularly for female clients and clients from more rural markets.

Data on SIM card sales and M-Pesa registrations was also collected to track the effectiveness of each TSR in being able to register new clients to M-Pesa. Additional data was collected through M-

Pesa on client activity after initial registration, to view how their activity on the platform progressed over time and to understand how the profile of client changed under different supply-side conditions. All client data was anonymized, and clients provided consent at the time of registration to have their anonymized registration and transaction data used for the study. Transaction data included the frequency and currency amount of each transaction that was executed from the time the customer was registered up to two months after the intervention concluded.

Demographic data on TSRs was also collected at the time of hiring. Additional data was collected on the market location and sales of each TSR each day, and communication between TSRs and study coordinators was maintained to document TSR turnover and any issues that were observed or reported at various markets.

3.2 Key Outcomes

Key outcomes include the number of new SIM cards registered, the number of new M-Pesa accounts created and the number of new M-Pesa accounts that are ever used. These outcomes are measured as counts at the market day level. We also present the “conversion rate” of new M-Pesa accounts which is the share of new SIM cards that also open an M-Pesa account.

For outcomes that leverage the team randomization, we conduct our analysis at the market day level; outcomes are calculated for each day in each market, and we compare average differences in these outcomes between markets that were randomly assigned to male TSR teams on a given day to markets that were randomly assigned to female TSR teams on that day. For our interrupted time series analysis of the incentive program, we assess outcomes at the day level.

3.3 Analysis

3.3.1 Interrupted Time Series Analysis

Our interrupted time series analyses assesses the extent to which the introduction of the financial incentive was successful in motivating TSRs, and particularly female TSRs, to introduce clients, particularly female and more rural clients, to M-Pesa. We use the following specification to estimate the effects of the incentive:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_d = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 FTSR_d + \beta_2 I_d + \beta_3 d + \beta_4 (FTSR_d \cdot I_d) \\
 & + \beta_5 (FTSR_d \cdot d) + \beta_6 (I_d \cdot d) + \beta_7 (FTSR_d \cdot I_d \cdot d) + \varepsilon_d
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

Here, Y_d is the outcome on day d , $FTSR_d$ is a binary indicator for the female TSR team gender, and I_d is a binary indicator for the implementation of the incentive in that day. For this analysis, each observation is the average of outcome Y for either male TSR teams or female TSR teams on day d , resulting in two observations per day over the study period (a male TSR team average and a female TSR team average, respectively).

3.3.2 Market Day Level Analysis

In order to identify the causal impact of female TSRs relative to male TSRs, we exploit the experimental variation that was induced among the sub-sample of clients who were contacted by male or female TSR teams in the ten markets. Given that TSR teams were randomly assigned to different markets each day, we conduct adjusted analyses for our key outcomes at the market-day level, which is the unit of randomization. We estimate the following:

$$Y_{md} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FTSR_{md} + \beta_2 I_{md} + \delta_m + \delta_d + \varepsilon_{md} \quad (2)$$

where Y_{md} is the outcome for market m on day of the week d . In addition, we include an indicator for market days when the incentive program was implemented, I_{md} , as well as market-level and day of the week fixed effects (δ_m and δ_d , respectively). As these analyses are conducted at the market-day level, the unit of randomization, we present heteroskedastic-robust standard errors in our specifications. For analyses where our outcomes are assessed at a finer level (e.g. client, transaction), standard errors are clustered at the market-day level. The main coefficient of interest, β_1 , describes the adjusted mean differences in client outcomes for clients who are contacted by female TSR teams relative to clients who are contacted by male TSR teams. Finally, we present robustness checks to account for the fact that we have a limited number of teams that are randomized across markets.

3.4 Sub-Group Analyses

We conduct a range of sub-group analyses to identify potential heterogeneity in the impacts of being contacted by female TSRs relative to male TSRs. We particularly explore the impacts of gendered TSR teams on female clients and clients who are approached in more rural (far) markets, both of which were part of the incentive program. Using the TSR test scores from the hiring assessment, we calculate average test scores for each TSR team and conduct sub-group analyses to compare differences in outcomes between teams, both by gender (male versus female teams) and by relative

test performance (higher-scoring teams versus lower-scoring teams). Findings from these analyses are presented in the Appendix.

4 Results

4.1 Sample Description and Balance

Over a 22-week period between December 15, 2017 and May 15, 2018, 12 TSR teams engaged with a total of 6,564 clients across 10 markets and: 1) registered clients with new Vodafone SIM cards; and 2) enrolled clients into M-Pesa. Of these new clients, 52 percent (3,465 in total) were converted to M-Pesa. Among converted clients, the time from registering for a new SIM card to conversion to M-Pesa was relatively short, with 40 percent of M-Pesa clients converting to M-Pesa on the same day when they registered for a new SIM card, while 80 percent of clients converted to M-Pesa within a week of registering for their SIM card. The average client who was registered for a new SIM card was 30.2 years old, 98.9 percent of clients were under the age of 50, and 36.2 percent of newly registered clients were women. Of the 17 total weeks that clients were tracked, transactions were made on 41.4 percent of the days. Clients made an average of 1.79 transactions valued at an average of 474.61 Meticals per week. [Table A1](#) in the Appendix presents a balance table of random assignment of TSR teams to each of the 10 different markets over the study period, and [Table A2](#) in the Appendix presents additional descriptive statistics for each market. On average, markets were equally likely to be assigned to be visited by male and female TSR teams, although male TSR teams were marginally more likely to be assigned to visit the three more remotely located markets (Murriase, Chiequele, and Marratane). In addition, TSR teams were equally likely to be working in these markets on any given day of the week. Taken together, the findings from the balance table provide evidence to support the randomized assignment of TSR teams to each of the markets over the study period.

[Table 1](#) presents mean outcome comparisons between clients who were registered by male TSR or female TSR teams. On average, male TSR teams reached an average of 4.8 more clients per market day relative to female TSR teams. However, the M-Pesa conversion rate for female TSR teams is significantly higher (7.8 p.p.) than the conversion rate for male TSR teams. Moreover, male and female teams were equally likely to create a new M-Pesa account that was actually used; however, we find that clients who registered with female TSRs had 0.72 fewer M-Pesa transactions over the past 4 weeks relative to clients who registered with male TSRs. We observe no significant differences

in transaction frequency or transaction amount between clients who were registered for M-Pesa by female TSR teams and clients who were registered by male TSR teams; in fact, clients who were registered by female TSR teams were found to conduct transactions of marginally higher value (by 267 Meticals, or 4.18 USD) compared to clients registered by male TSR teams. We also find that female clients were equally likely to be registered for SIM cards and to M-Pesa by female TSR teams compared to male TSR teams.

Table 1 About Here.

4.2 Market-Day Analysis Results

Findings from a regression-adjusted market-day level analysis are presented in [Table 2](#). We find that female TSR teams registered 4.47 fewer clients, including 1.29 fewer female clients and 1.64 fewer rural clients, to SIM cards per market-day compared to male TSR teams (column 1). Among clients who were registered, however, female TSR teams were 7.4 percentage points (14.5 percent) more likely to be successful at converting clients to M-Pesa than male TSR teams (column 4). Moreover, there was no significant difference in the number of M-Pesa clients registered per market day between female and male TSR teams (column 2), nor was there any difference in M-Pesa account use by clients by TSR gender (column 3).

Table 2 About Here.

4.3 Interrupted Time Series Results

[Figure 2](#) present results from the interrupted time series (ITS) analysis on the average number of new M-Pesa clients enrolled by TSR team gender over the study period⁷. [Table 3](#) and [Table 4](#) present ITS results for a range of client-level outcomes by TSR team gender. Concordant with our market-day results, we note that female TSR teams reached a lower absolute number of clients per day relative to male TSR teams before the incentive was introduced. We also observe a decrease over time in the rate of new SIM and M-Pesa clients enrolled per day by male TSR teams prior to the introduction of the incentive. In contrast, the rate of new clients who signed up for new SIM accounts and registered with M-Pesa, particularly female and rural clients, actually increased over time for female TSR teams before the incentive was introduced. The introduction of the incentive had a generally strong and positive effect on client enrollment to both SIM cards as well as to M-Pesa.

Similarly to the market-day analysis, we find that female TSR teams were 24.4 percentage points (51.8 percent) more successful in converting clients whom they did register to M-Pesa relative to male TSR teams. Moreover, the M-Pesa conversion rate following the introduction of the incentive increased at a significantly higher rate for female TSR teams relative to male TSR teams ([Table 4](#)).

Figure 2 About Here.

Table 3 About Here.

Table 4 About Here.

To confirm our findings, we conduct a supplementary ITS analysis on transaction-level outcomes, the results for which are presented in [Table A3](#) in the Appendix. Both the number and value of transactions among registered M-Pesa clients increased over the 22 week period. In terms of transaction behavior, we find small and insignificant differences in transaction frequency and positive, but insignificant, differences in the average transaction value among clients who were registered by female TSR teams relative to clients who were registered by male TSR teams. Transaction activity, both in terms of the number and value of transactions, declined among clients following the introduction of the incentive even though the number of SIM and M-Pesa registrations increased over this same period. Across our ITS analyses, we find no significant differences in transaction outcomes between male TSR and female TSR teams after the introduction of the incentive.

4.4 Sub-Group Analyses

We conduct several subgroup analyses to explore potential mechanisms. First, we compare the impact of TSR team assignment before and after the introduction of the incentive. [Table A4](#), together with model results in [Table A5](#), show that prior to the introduction of the incentive, female TSR teams, on average, registered fewer clients to SIM accounts and M-Pesa accounts per market-day and were as successful at converting clients to M-Pesa as male TSR teams. Following the introduction of the incentive, female TSR teams continued to register fewer SIM clients relative to male TSR teams; however, they were 12.6 percentage points (24.7 percent) more likely than male TSR teams to convert registered SIM clients to M-Pesa. As a result, female TSR teams were, on average, able to enroll as many M-Pesa clients per market-day as male TSR teams. The findings from [Table A4](#) also suggest that average transaction values for clients who were enrolled by female TSR teams are higher than

clients who were enrolled by male TSR teams. Taken together, our findings suggest that female TSR teams were more effective than male TSR teams at converting clients to M-Pesa before the incentive, and they became even more successful after the incentive was introduced.

In [Table A6](#) and [Table A7](#), we explore heterogeneous effects of TSR team assignment for female clients and clients from more remote markets, both of which were targeted by the incentive program. Our findings are consistent with the main results: while male TSR teams recruited more SIM clients overall, female TSR teams were more successful at converting SIM clients to active M-Pesa users. Notably, in more remote areas, clients registered by female TSR teams exhibited higher transaction activity, both in the number and value of transactions within the past four weeks, relative to those registered by male TSR teams. These results reinforce our finding that male and female agents may differ in how they engage clients along various points of the service adoption pathway.

In [Table A9](#), we present results from our comparisons of higher-scoring TSR teams against lower-scoring TSR teams by gender, using the average test scores of each team as an indicator for performance potential (see [Table A8](#)). We find few significant differences in outcomes when comparing higher-scoring teams against lower-scoring teams within gender; we find no difference in TSR performance on SIM and M-Pesa registration between lower-scoring (fe)male teams and higher-scoring (fe)male teams. When comparing across gendered teams, we find that higher-scoring male TSR teams were not more likely to outperform lower-scoring female TSR teams. Lower-scoring female TSR teams did outperform lower-scoring male TSR teams in converting clients to M-Pesa, but not in daily SIM registration. In line with our main findings, we see that higher-scoring female TSR teams outperformed both higher-scoring as well as lower-scoring male TSR teams in converting clients to M-Pesa, though male TSR teams were more successful at registering clients to SIM accounts.

The Supplementary Materials include additional robustness checks and sensitivity analyses, such as results from a randomization inference exercise and adjustments for multiple hypothesis testing, which further support our main findings.

5 Discussion

In this study, we analyze the impact of modifying the hiring, training and incentives of MM agents to improve the penetration of MM access and use among Mozambican populations, particularly women living in rural and remote areas. We find that female agent teams sell fewer new SIM cards overall relative to male agent teams but are more effective in converting new SIM clients to MMAs. These

patterns suggest that female agents may be less successful at initiating contact with clients relative to male agents, but may be relatively more successful at retaining client attention and engagement following a successful first contact.

We find that male and female agents may have distinct comparative advantages when recruiting and converting clients to MM. Our analysis further suggests that female and male agents may adopt different strategies when provided with incentives, potentially reflecting underlying gender-specific differences in constraints or opportunities, such as mobility, skills, or client networks, that shape how they engage with clients at different margins of the registration process. Male agents may be more effective at engaging with clients at the initial SIM registration stage (the “extensive margin”), while female agents may be more successful at deepening engagement and converting clients to active M-Pesa use (the “intensive margin”). These patterns are consistent with prior evidence documenting gender-based differences in communication, trust-building, or social proximity to female clients (Chamboko et al., 2021; Penicaud-Scharwatt and Minischetti, 2014). They also imply that diversifying the gender profile of MM agents could improve client engagement without altering overall enrollment of new clients, particularly among populations that may be less likely to adopt DFS under current conditions. Taken together, our experimental approach allows us to infer the success of female agents in engaging with clients relative to male agents, keeping the market environment constant; however, we acknowledge that there are many other reasons why men and women may differ in their success as MM agents. Additional research is needed to unpack the mechanisms that may be driving this finding.

Our results suggest that relatively low-cost incentives can increase the enrollment of women overall and women living in remote areas in particular. Incentives were effective in encouraging enrollment of women for both male and female TSR teams. Our supply-side variations are embedded within a suite of interventions that seek to improve and enhance the overall effectiveness of TSR agents in enrolling clients to MM. Future research is needed to assess whether similar interventions could work in settings with less intensive training and team composition protocols.

Our study allows us to effectively test the role of agent-client concordance and incentives on MM adoption and engagement in a setting where the market for MM, both in terms of DFS penetration and phone ownership, is less mature and where the gender gap in MM access is larger relative to other Sub-Saharan African contexts (e.g. Kenya, Tanzania, Ghana). We recognize that while the

effects of our supply-side interventions may be larger in Mozambique than in other contexts where markets for MM are more established, it is also possible that the impacts of our interventions may attenuate over time as MM access continues to expand in Mozambique.

Because we rely exclusively on administrative records, our study is not able to assess how clients felt about their enrollment experiences. While we are able to document the intervention’s impact on transaction frequency and amount, we do not have more information about the types of transactions that our clients are undertaking, which would have allowed us to identify how transaction behavior and access to credit may differ by gender. The lack of granularity in our administrative data also limits our ability to match specific agents with clients whom they served, which would allowed us to more precisely infer variation in agent performance within a team (e.g. whether there were some high-performing / low-performing agents within a team) and whether the variation in individual agent performance differed by gender. However, we note that the evidence on outcomes by TSR team “quality”, as measured by the average test score of the team, is mixed, suggesting that the scores that TSRs received on their assessments may be an imperfect indicator of agent performance and may, in fact, act as a barrier to identifying and recruiting qualified TSRs, and female TSRs in particular. More generally, our inference from a small sample of 12 agents being distributed across just 10 markets might not be generalizable to the relative performance of the broader population of male and female MM agents in Mozambique.

Ensuring equitable access to DFS has been recognized as a pathway to sustainable development ([GSM Association, 2019c](#); [World Bank, 2012](#)). The expansion of MM and DFS as part of larger social programs also has significant implications for improving population health, reducing poverty, and advancing social and economic well-being ([Hamani et al., 2023](#); [World Bank, 2022](#)). DFS are a promising opportunity for promoting women’s economic empowerment and have been shown to facilitate women’s access to transactions, savings, credit, and insurance. Nonetheless, many women, particularly in remote areas, have not benefited from this expansion. Evidence from our study suggests that attempts to expand access should consider how to more effectively engage mobile network operators in order to expand MM services to populations that are less well served by current efforts. The increased use of MM will require public-private partnerships to allow multilaterals and governments to effectively determine how MM operators can improve equity in service provision. To this end, the expansion of access to such services will require cross-sectoral coordination between

consumers, facilitators of MM and DFS, and higher-level managers of digital public infrastructure.

Endnotes

¹For example, an impact evaluation of a microfinance institution (MFI) in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) documented evidence of assortative matching between MFI agents and clients by gender, where female clients were more likely to engage and transact with female MFI agents than male clients ([Chamboko et al., 2021](#)).

²According to a 2016 USAID study in Mozambique, when respondents were asked what features they desired in their phones, more women than men named MM as a desired feature (17 percent of women compared to 14 percent of men) ([USAID, 2016](#)).

³Only eight markets were part of the study at any one time; two of the original eight markets became inaccessible after a cyclone caused a bridge to break in week 4 of the study. As a result, the intervention was reassigned to two other markets.

⁴Female TSRs were hired even if they did not score in the top 12. As shown in [Table A8](#), the average score on the post-training exam was higher for men than for women, with the average exam score for the lower ranking male TSR team being higher than the average test score for the higher female TSR team. As part of our analysis, we explore heterogeneity in the impact of the interventions by TSR performance on this screening assessment; results from this analysis are presented in [Table A9](#) in the Appendix.

⁵These markets were identified by M-Pesa as rural and hard to reach because they were 40 minutes or more by bus on an unpaved road from Nampula’s city center.

⁶We note that this period was marked by the occurrence of multiple cyclones and tropical storms across Mozambique.

⁷The ITS results for the average number of new female M-Pesa clients and rural female M-Pesa clients enrolled by TSR team gender are presented in the Supplementary Materials.

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6 Figures

Figure 1: Experimental Diagram and Timeline

Figure 2: Number of New M-Pesa Clients per Week by TSR Gender

Note: Data collection and market activities were severely affected in March 2018 due to tropical Cyclone Idai, between day 50 and day 83.

7 Tables

Table 1: Comparison of Outcomes by Male TSR Group and Female TSR Group, Market-Day Level

Variable	(1) Male TSR	(2) Female TSR	(3) Difference (F - M)
Total No. of Clients, Mkt. Day	19.917	15.148	-4.769***
Total No. of M-Pesa Clients, Mkt. Day	9.710	8.824	-0.886
Total M-Pesa use, Mkt. Day	8.527	7.795	-0.731
Tot. M-Pesa use in last 4 Wks, Mkt. Day	3.405	2.682	-0.723**
M-Pesa Conversion Rate	0.506	0.584	0.078***
Convert within 1 Wk	0.741	0.818	0.078***
Avg. Number of Transactions	2.115	2.038	-0.078
Avg. Value of Transactions	472.946	740.711	267.765
Client Sex	0.353	0.329	-0.024
Observations	169	176	345

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

The unit of observation is the market-day.

Table 2: Male TSR vs. Female TSR - Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
A: All Clients				
Female TSR	-4.473*** [-7.332, -1.614]	-0.775 [-2.527, 0.976]	-0.579 [-2.182, 1.025]	0.074** [0.014, 0.133]
Observations	345	345	345	345
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
B: Female Clients				
Female TSR	-1.290** [-2.558, -0.022]	0.096 [-0.854, 1.045]	0.145 [-0.745, 1.035]	0.008 [-0.038, 0.053]
Observations	345	283	283	345
Control Mean	7.01	4.01	3.56	0.19
C: Rural Clients				
Female TSR	-1.644* [-3.369, 0.081]	-0.336 [-3.357, 2.685]	0.091 [-2.692, 2.875]	0.018 [-0.012, 0.049]
Observations	345	116	116	345
Control Mean	7.59	9.03	7.75	0.19
D: Rural Female Clients				
Female TSR	-0.653 [-1.433, 0.128]	0.488 [-0.744, 1.719]	0.585 [-0.556, 1.727]	-0.005 [-0.034, 0.024]
Observations	345	104	104	345
Control Mean	2.76	3.21	2.77	0.08
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include whether the incentive was implemented, market and day of the week fixed effects. Heteroskedastic-robust standard errors are presented. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 3: ITS Analysis of Incentive - Day

	No. of New M-Pesa Clients per Day	No. of New Female M-Pesa Clients per Day	No. of New Rural M-Pesa Clients per Day	No. of New Rural Female M-Pesa Clients per Day
Time (Week)	-0.206*** [-0.343, -0.068]	-0.006 [-0.070, 0.058]	-0.203** [-0.363, -0.043]	-0.063** [-0.118, -0.009]
Female TSR	-4.544* [-9.639, 0.551]	0.132 [-1.755, 2.020]	-9.491*** [-15.697, -3.286]	-2.868*** [-4.578, -1.157]
Female TSR \times Time	0.074 [-0.076, 0.223]	-0.031 [-0.104, 0.042]	0.302** [0.021, 0.582]	0.142*** [0.045, 0.240]
Incentive	29.373*** [18.421, 40.325]	8.882*** [3.737, 14.028]	18.484*** [7.469, 29.499]	6.060*** [2.171, 9.949]
Time \times Incentive	0.002 [-0.232, 0.237]	-0.082 [-0.185, 0.022]	0.112 [-0.119, 0.343]	0.057 [-0.023, 0.137]
Female TSR \times Incentive	-2.768 [-17.231, 11.696]	2.717 [-4.421, 9.856]	-14.802 [-35.754, 6.151]	-5.430 [-14.411, 3.550]
Female TSR \times Time \times Incentive	-0.051 [-0.366, 0.264]	0.025 [-0.123, 0.174]	-0.309 [-0.692, 0.075]	-0.208** [-0.378, -0.037]
Constant	15.008*** [10.639, 19.377]	3.013*** [1.508, 4.519]	12.570*** [7.416, 17.724]	2.975*** [1.426, 4.523]
Observations	214	192	99	90

Notes: The unit of analysis is the day by TSR gender, where average outcomes are calculated for each day by TSR gender. All models are estimated using interrupted time series specifications to identify the impact of the introduction of the M4A incentive, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. The variable Female TSR is a binary indicator for TSR gender, the variable Time indicates the day (days 1-152), and the variable Incentive is a binary indicator for the introduction of the incentive. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 4: ITS Analysis of Incentive - Day

	New SIM Accounts per Day	M-Pesa Accounts Used per Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Week
Time (Week)	-0.444*** [-0.664, -0.224]	-0.133** [-0.241, -0.025]	0.007*** [0.004, 0.010]
Female TSR	-11.762*** [-19.986, -3.538]	-4.013** [-7.598, -0.427]	0.244*** [0.069, 0.419]
Female TSR \times Time	0.255** [0.014, 0.496]	0.058 [-0.057, 0.173]	-0.013*** [-0.021, -0.004]
Incentive	62.694*** [43.227, 82.160]	26.359*** [16.638, 36.079]	-0.522*** [-0.734, -0.309]
Time \times Incentive	0.129 [-0.324, 0.582]	-0.078 [-0.283, 0.128]	-0.008*** [-0.012, -0.004]
Female TSR \times Incentive	-19.415 [-43.604, 4.774]	-2.226 [-15.282, 10.830]	0.866*** [0.330, 1.402]
Female TSR \times Time \times Incentive	-0.224 [-0.781, 0.334]	-0.019 [-0.302, 0.264]	0.014*** [0.005, 0.023]
Constant	28.473*** [21.399, 35.547]	10.609*** [7.488, 13.729]	0.471*** [0.396, 0.545]
Observations	214	214	214

Notes: The unit of analysis is the day by TSR gender, where average outcomes are calculated for each day by TSR gender. All models are estimated using interrupted time series specifications to identify the impact of the introduction of the M4A incentive, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. The variable Female TSR is a binary indicator for TSR gender, the variable Time indicates the day (days 1-152), and the variable Incentive is a binary indicator for the introduction of the incentive. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

8 Appendix Tables

Table A1: Balance Table of Team Visits by TSR Team Gender

	(1)	(2)	(3)
Variable	TSR Male	TSR Female	Difference (F - M)
Anchilo	0.136	0.125	-0.011
Chiequele	0.109	0.094	-0.015
Elipisse	0.016	0.027	0.012
Marratane	0.117	0.094	-0.023
Moacoanvela	0.125	0.133	0.008
Murriase	0.132	0.086	-0.046*
Murripula	0.113	0.148	0.036
Nameteca	0.109	0.113	0.004
Namiepe	0.097	0.109	0.012
Rapale	0.012	0.039	0.027**
Far Market	0.358	0.273	-0.085**
Sunday	0.019	0.016	-0.004
Monday	0.163	0.164	0.001
Tuesday	0.163	0.164	0.001
Wednesday	0.167	0.172	0.005
Thursday	0.163	0.164	0.001
Friday	0.156	0.156	0.001
Saturday	0.167	0.164	-0.003
Observations	257	256	513

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

The unit of observation is the group-day (for example, Female TSR Group A on December 15, 2018 or Male TSR Group B on January 3, 2019).

Table A2: Descriptive Statistics by Market

Market Name	No. of Agents in Market before M4A	Distance to Market from Nampula (km)	Time to Market from Nampula (min)			Road Type to Market
			Car	Bus	Taxi Motorcycle	
Marratane	7	25	25	40	25	Off road
Anchilo	10	18	20	35	25	Asphalt
Namiepe	2	9	15	30	15	Off road
Rapale	10	14	15	30	20	Asphalt
Murriase	2	22	20	40	30	Off road
Controle	1	10	10	30	15	Asphalt
Moacoanvela	16	4	15	20	10	Asphalt
Chiequele	2	36	45	75	60	Off road
Namateca	36	11	20	30	15	Off road
Elipisse	15	8	15	30	15	Off road

Table A3: ITS Analysis of Incentive - Week Enrolled

	No. of Transactions per Week	Value of Transactions per Week
Time (Week)	0.110**	20.457***
	[0.010, 0.210]	[6.319, 34.595]
Female TSR	-0.085	45.504
	[-0.619, 0.448]	[-94.046, 185.053]
Female TSR \times Time	-0.004	-20.034*
	[-0.156, 0.149]	[-40.758, 0.691]
Incentive	2.044*	476.713
	[-0.317, 4.404]	[-140.807, 1094.232]
Time \times Incentive	-0.674**	-155.066*
	[-1.248, -0.099]	[-320.081, 9.948]
Female TSR \times Incentive	1.491	-200.940
	[-4.744, 7.726]	[-915.972, 514.092]
Female TSR \times Time \times Incentive	0.222	260.428
	[-1.807, 2.251]	[-100.586, 621.442]
Constant	0.166	72.085*
	[-0.201, 0.532]	[-13.010, 157.181]
Observations	34	34

Notes: The unit of analysis is the week enrolled by TSR gender, where average outcomes are calculated for each week by TSR gender. All models are estimated using interrupted time series specifications to identify the impact of the introduction of the M4A incentive, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. The variable Female TSR is a binary indicator for TSR gender, the variable Time indicates the week (weeks 1-17), and the variable Incentive is a binary indicator for the introduction of the incentive. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table A4: Comparison of Outcomes within TSR Groups Pre- and Post-Incentive, Market-Day Level

Variable	(1) Before Incentive	(2) After Incentive	(3) Difference (After - Before)
A: Female TSRs			
Total No. of Clients, Mkt. Day	6.803	20.155	13.352***
Total No. of M-Pesa Clients, Mkt. Day	4.061	11.682	7.621***
Total M-Pesa use, Mkt. Day	2.636	10.891	8.255***
Tot. M-Pesa use in last 4 Wks, Mkt. Day	1.589	3.487	1.898***
M-Pesa Conversion Rate	0.592	0.579	-0.013
Convert within 1 Wk	0.782	0.838	0.056
Avg. Number of Transactions	1.817	2.153	0.337
Avg. Value of Transactions	330.189	955.564	625.375
Client Sex	0.258	0.371	0.112***
Observations	66	110	176
B: Male TSRs			
Total No. of Clients, Mkt. Day	10.678	24.873	14.195***
Total No. of M-Pesa Clients, Mkt. Day	5.983	11.709	5.726***
Total M-Pesa use, Mkt. Day	4.356	10.764	6.408***
Tot. M-Pesa use in last 4 Wks, Mkt. Day	2.132	4.329	2.197***
M-Pesa Conversion Rate	0.601	0.455	-0.146***
Convert within 1 Wk	0.676	0.774	0.099**
Avg. Number of Transactions	1.912	2.221	0.309
Avg. Value of Transactions	287.811	569.143	281.331
Client Sex	0.265	0.400	0.136***
Observations	59	110	169

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

The unit of observation is the market-day.

Table A5: Stratified Analysis of Male TSR vs. Female TSR by Incentive Period - Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
A: Pre-Incentive Period				
Female TSR	-3.471** [-6.311, -0.631]	-1.801** [-3.561, -0.042]	-1.633** [-2.915, -0.351]	-0.008 [-0.137, 0.121]
Observations	125	125	125	125
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
B: Post-Incentive Period				
Female TSR	-4.730** [-8.997, -0.462]	-0.051 [-2.613, 2.512]	0.076 [-2.337, 2.488]	0.126*** [0.061, 0.191]
Observations	220	220	220	220
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include market and day of the week fixed effects. Heteroskedastic-robust standard errors are presented. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table A6: Interaction Analysis, Male TSR vs. Female TSR - Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
Female TSR	-6.662*** [-11.685, -1.639]	-2.690* [-5.614, 0.234]	-2.505* [-5.078, 0.068]	0.140* [-0.012, 0.291]
Client Sex	-3.903 [-15.367, 7.561]	-2.234 [-8.215, 3.748]	-1.864 [-7.187, 3.459]	0.076 [-0.230, 0.382]
Female TSR \times Client Sex	7.376 [-6.445, 21.198]	5.368 [-2.704, 13.440]	4.985 [-2.271, 12.242]	-0.183 [-0.577, 0.212]
Market is far (1 = Yes)	4.265 [-4.509, 13.038]	0.777 [-4.115, 5.669]	-0.045 [-4.359, 4.269]	-0.080 [-0.266, 0.106]
Female TSR \times Market is far (1 = Yes)	-6.207 [-15.548, 3.134]	-1.970 [-7.288, 3.349]	-1.127 [-5.909, 3.655]	-0.020 [-0.234, 0.195]
Market is far (1 = Yes) \times Client Sex	-11.379 [-27.669, 4.911]	-5.795 [-13.990, 2.400]	-4.576 [-11.877, 2.724]	0.196 [-0.220, 0.612]
Female TSR \times Market is far (1 = Yes) \times Client Sex	13.261 [-7.628, 34.150]	5.483 [-6.322, 17.288]	4.503 [-6.301, 15.306]	0.069 [-0.497, 0.634]
Observations	345	345	345	345
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include whether the incentive was implemented, market and day of the week fixed effects. Heteroskedastic-robust standard errors are presented. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Table A7: Analysis of Treatment Male TSR versus Treatment Female TSR, Interaction with Client Sex and Rural Client

	Total No. of Transactions in First 8 Wks.	Total Value of Transactions in First 8 Wks.	No. of Transactions in Last 4 Wks.	Value of Transactions in Last 4 Wks.
Female TSR	-0.286	-383.728	-2.614**	-391.838**
	[-8.934, 8.361]	[-3813.922, 3046.465]	[-4.773, -0.456]	[-759.684, -23.992]
Client Sex (1 = Female)	-4.251	-2254.942	-1.574	-282.135
	[-10.766, 2.264]	[-5675.598, 1165.714]	[-3.631, 0.483]	[-630.358, 66.087]
Female TSR \times Client Sex (1 = Female)	-1.261	630.793	1.683	300.020
	[-11.865, 9.343]	[-3977.696, 5239.281]	[-0.602, 3.968]	[-79.147, 679.187]
Market is far (1 = Yes)	-1.968	-208.498	-2.137*	-281.024*
	[-8.580, 4.644]	[-3143.181, 2726.186]	[-4.624, 0.350]	[-567.128, 5.079]
Female TSR \times Market is far (1 = Yes)	-1.781	-457.490	3.415**	412.272**
	[-12.311, 8.749]	[-4205.424, 3290.444]	[0.793, 6.038]	[45.772, 778.773]
Female TSR \times Client Sex (1 = Female) \times Market is far (1 = Yes)	-4.777	-3364.086	-2.261	-271.145
	[-18.068, 8.514]	[-9338.829, 2610.658]	[-5.467, 0.946]	[-670.889, 128.599]
Observations	267	267	195	195
Control Mean	1.08	313.47	0.17	36.88
p-value: Male TSR = Female TSR for Male Clients - Over Last 8 Weeks	0.95	0.83	0.02	0.04
p-value: Male TSR = Female TSR for Female Clients	0.81	0.79	0.15	0.12
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: The unit of analysis is the client. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. Covariates include: age (in four age groups), whether the incentive was implemented, and market and day of the week fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the market-day level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Table A8: TSR Descriptive Statistics: TSR Exam Scores

TSR ID	TSR Group No.	Group No.	TSR Test Score (out of 10)	Group Avg. Test Score
212	1	Female Group A	9	8.0
336	1	Female Group A	6	
093	1	Female Group A	9	
052	2	Female Group B	7	6.6
958	2	Female Group B	6	
959	2	Female Group B	7	
271	3	Male Group A	8	8.3
060	3	Male Group A	9	
556	3	Male Group A	8	
276	4	Male Group B	9	8.5
406	4	Male Group B	8	
614	4	Male Group B	9	
880	4	Male Group B	8	

Table A9: Comparison of TSR Team Performance: Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
A: Male TSR Group B (High) vs. Female TSR Group A (High)				
Female TSR	-3.113 [-7.365, 1.138]	0.198 [-2.329, 2.725]	0.160 [-2.174, 2.494]	0.084* [-0.007, 0.175]
Observations	167	167	167	167
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
B: Male TSR Group B (High) vs. Female TSR Group B (Low)				
Female TSR	-3.671 [-8.369, 1.026]	-0.980 [-3.761, 1.802]	-0.983 [-3.554, 1.588]	0.058 [-0.037, 0.153]
Observations	152	152	152	152
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
C: Male TSR Group A (Low) vs. Female TSR Group A (High)				
Female TSR	-4.378** [-8.258, -0.499]	0.028 [-2.412, 2.469]	0.177 [-2.081, 2.436]	0.101** [0.023, 0.178]
Observations	178	178	178	178
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
D: Male TSR Group B (Low) vs. Female TSR Group B (Low)				
Female TSR	-5.333** [-9.706, -0.961]	-1.103 [-3.675, 1.469]	-0.969 [-3.294, 1.357]	0.080* [-0.011, 0.170]
Observations	163	163	163	163
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
E: Female TSR Group A (High) vs. Female TSR Group B (Low)				
Female Group B	-1.345 [-5.101, 2.411]	-1.845 [-4.291, 0.600]	-1.829 [-4.096, 0.439]	-0.036 [-0.122, 0.050]
Observations	169	169	169	169
Control Mean	15.45	9.41	8.38	0.59
F: Male TSR Group A (Low) vs. Male TSR Group B (High)				
Male Group B	-0.455 [-5.358, 4.448]	0.709 [-1.941, 3.358]	0.764 [-1.655, 3.184]	0.035 [-0.058, 0.127]
Observations	161	161	161	161
Control Mean	20.57	9.86	8.58	0.50
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, with 95 percent confidence intervals presented in brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include whether the incentive was implemented, market and day of the week fixed effects. Heteroskedastic-robust standard errors are presented. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.